

DATA-DRIVEN PREDICTION OF UNSTEADY MIXER OUTLET TEMPERATURE IN HIGH-ALTITUDE ENGINE INLET SYSTEMS USING A STACKING FRAMEWORK WITH AN ERROR COMPENSATION MODEL

Chenchen Wang

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China

Keqiang Miao

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China

Chunyan Hu

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China
(Corresponding Author)

Jiaxian Sun

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China

Wei Li

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China

Hanling Xu

1. Key Laboratory of Light-Duty Gas-Turbine/Institute of Engineering Thermophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100190, China
2. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China
3. National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Light-duty Gas-turbine Beijing 100049, China

ABSTRACT

To address the deviation between the actual outlet temperature and the theoretically calculated temperature in a

mixer where two airflows with different temperatures and pressures are blended, a temperature prediction method based on Stacking framework combined with an error compensation

model was proposed. In the first layer of the framework, support vector machine (SVM) and backpropagation (BP) neural network algorithm were employed as base learners to preliminarily train the original data. Subsequently, the simulation results of the mechanistic mixer model and actual temperature data were utilized to train a Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT)-based error compensation model, which was incorporated into the second layer. The meta-model in the second layer adopted the random forest (RF) algorithm to integrate the compensated outputs and generate the final prediction. This approach not only captures the nonlinear relationships among features but also exploits the temporal dependencies embedded in the temperature data. Simulation results demonstrate that, compared with a standalone RF model, the proposed hybrid Stacking framework achieves a 0.25% reduction in root mean squared error and a 1.97% improvement in the coefficient of determination, thereby significantly improving prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Unsteady mixing; Stacking framework; Data-driven; Error compensation

1. INTRODUCTION

Altitude Ground Test Facility (AGTF) is a critical equipment for high-altitude simulation testing of aero-engines. Accurately simulating the high-altitude intake environmental conditions is essential to ensure the reliability and precision of high-altitude test results [1, 2]. During the process of simulating high-altitude intake environmental conditions, the accurate simulation of intake temperature is particularly significant. However, in practical high-altitude intake simulations, the airflow mixing process deviates from the ideal assumption and is influenced by various factors, leading to significant discrepancies between the actual outlet temperature and the theoretically calculated temperature [3]. The primary contributing factors can be summarized as follows:

1. **Energy Loss:** In theory, the air should ideally mix uniformly. In practice, however, the presence of components such as pipes and valves introduces unavoidable energy losses. Pipe wall roughness, local throttling effects in valves, and flow-wall interactions generate friction and heat conduction, which dissipate energy and lead to deviations between the actual outlet temperature and the theoretical value.

2. **Non-uniform Mixing:** The mixing process in real flows is rarely homogeneous [4]. Fluid dynamic effects, such as resistance, curvature of ducts, and localized vortices, induce significant spatial variations in intake temperature, pressure and flow rate [5]. Consequently, the outlet temperature distribution often exhibits non-uniformity, deviating considerably from the theoretical average value.

3. **Slow Mixing:** In theory, the airflow is expected to rapidly reach a steady state mixed state. In practice, however, equipment design limitations, flow characteristics, and variations in flow velocity cause a slow mixing process. The inertia of airflow prevents instantaneous adjustment, leading to delayed stabilization and reduced accuracy of the outlet temperature. In some cases, this stabilization period is

prolonged, further amplifying the discrepancy between theoretical and measured outlet temperatures.

Therefore, although the theoretical model can calculate the intake temperature based on known physical formulas and simplified assumptions, the non-ideal behavior such as energy dissipation, non-uniform mixing, and delayed response cause significant deviations from the theoretical prediction. For instance, in a certain engine test, the comparison between theoretical and actual outlet temperature is shown in figure 1. It can be observed that the actual heating process exhibits a slower response, with heating rate considerably lower than that predicted by the theoretical model, and the steady-state temperature differs by approximately 8K.

Further analysis indicates that the major sources of error include:

1. The slow mixing rate and long mixing time in the airflow mixing process. From the analysis of existing high-altitude engine test data, the mixing rate in the mixer for different operating points ranges from 0.3 to 0.85 °C/min.

2. Response delay in mixing process [6]. Due to the large volume of the mixer cavity, changes in inlet flow temperature and mass flow rate do not immediately reflect at the outlet, resulting in a clear delay in temperature response.

3. Before the air from different routes enters the mixer, part of the airflow is diverted to the rear cabin of the test rig for temperature regulation. This secondary flow affects the flow rate and pressure of the main stream, thereby influencing the outlet temperature. This coupling effect is typically neglected in simplified mechanistic models.

FIGURE 1 MIXER OUTLET TEMPERATURE COMPARISON CURVE

Many scholars have conducted extensive research on the temperature regulation process of high-altitude simulation systems. Zhu et al. [7] analyzed the dynamic heat transfer characteristics of the flow inside the pipes during high-altitude heating tests, considering the impact of local heat losses. Montgomery et al. [8, 9] studied the heat transfer characteristics of the J1/J2 turbine engine test cell and explored the effects of

different factors such as the metal mass, cavity volume, and airflow state of the intake system on the intake temperature change rate. Aiming at the control problem of large temperature delay of flight environment simulation system of altitude ground test facilities, Zhu et al. [10] proposed a two degree-of-freedom μ synthesis control design method to improve the control accuracy of temperature, considering temperature delay uncertainty. However, during studies on high-altitude intake systems, many scholars have focused on the impact of heat transfer on temperature, overlooking the coupling of variables between different components.

In the modeling process, there are various disturbance factors that cannot be corrected within the original mechanistic model. However, the hybrid modeling method based on mechanism and data-driven effectively solves this problem [11, 12]. Ning et al. [13] used a method based on mechanism and data fusion to effectively improve the accuracy of spacecraft control system modeling. Peng [14] addressed the nonlinear and strong hysteresis issues in the heating process of vacuum sintering furnaces by combining both mechanistic analysis and data-driven methods, compensating for the shortcomings of each method and establishing a temperature model more aligned with actual conditions. Yu [15] focused on the decomposition furnace, creating an outlet temperature prediction model based on an elastic network combined with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks, achieving neural network-based predictive control of the outlet temperature and effectively controlling the temperature of the decomposition furnace.

In view of the above problems and the difficulty in correcting the mechanism model of the intake temperature simulation system, this paper proposes a hybrid modeling method that integrates both mechanistic and data-driven methods. First, an accurate mechanistic model of the intake air temperature simulation system was established, and the ElasticNet Regression Algorithm was used to reduce the dimensionality of the data and screen out the features that have a greater impact on the mixer outlet temperature. Applying this model to predict the temperature of the intake air temperature simulation system verifies its feasibility and effectiveness.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Mixer Mechanism Model Construction

The schematic diagram of the mixer is shown in figure 2, where the positions of various measurement points are indicated. The secondary flow is used for component cooling and does not exceed 5% of the mainstream flow. The dataset employed in this study originates from high-altitude engine tests and comprises 11 characteristic variables, as summarized in table 1.

Table 1: MEASUREMENT PARAMETERS

Flow/Location	Mass Flow Rate	Pressure	Temperature
Ambient Air	W_n	P_n	T_n
Cooled Air	W_c	P_c	T_c

FIGURE 2: SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF MIXER

Airflows with different temperatures, pressures, and flow rates are mixed within the mixer. Considering the steady-state mixing process, the mass conservation equation can be expressed as [16] :

$$m_1 + m_2 = m_3 \quad (1)$$

The energy conservation equation can be expressed as:

$$m_1 C_{p1} T_1 + m_2 C_{p2} T_2 = m_3 C_{p3} T_3 \quad (2)$$

Combining equations (1) and (2), the mixed temperature is obtained as:

$$T_3 = \frac{m_1 C_{p1} T_1 + m_2 C_{p2} T_2}{(m_1 + m_2) \cdot C_{p3}} \quad (3)$$

where m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 represent the mass flow rates of the first, second, and mixed airflows, respectively, in kg/s , C_{p1} , C_{p2} , and C_{p3} are the specific heat capacities of the first, second, and mixed airflows, respectively, in $J/(kg \cdot K)$, and T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 are their corresponding temperatures in K .

If the specific heat capacity of air is assumed to remain constant during the mixing process, Equation (3) can be simplified as:

$$T_3 = \frac{m_1 T_1 + m_2 T_2}{(m_1 + m_2)} \quad (4)$$

This physical model only characterizes the steady-state behavior and fails to account for the response delay and dynamic disturbances present in real systems. To address these limitations, a first-order inertia element is introduced, which can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\tau \cdot \frac{dT_{cal_delay}(t)}{dt} + T_{cal_delay}(t) = T_{cal}(t) \quad (5)$$

where τ is the time constant of the system, reflecting the degree of delay, $T_{cal}(t)$ is the instantaneous outlet temperature computed from the energy conservation model, and $T_{cal_delay}(t)$ is the delayed (inertia-affected) outlet temperature.

By discretizing the differential equation using a forward Euler method, the model can be rewritten as:

$$T_{cal_delay}(t + \Delta t) = T_{cal_delay}(t) + \frac{\Delta t}{\tau} [T_{cal}(t) - T_{cal_delay}(t)] \quad (6)$$

where Δt is the sampling interval.

Figure 3 compares the actual outlet temperature, the theoretical prediction from the ideal physical model, and the output of the inertia-based model. By comparison, introducing a first-order inertia element improves the approximation of the actual temperature variation trend. However, the model still deviates considerably from the real temperature dynamics and exhibits a large steady-state error, indicating the need for further investigation to enhance its accuracy.

FIGURE 3: OUTLET TEMPERATURE COMPARISON: PHYSICAL MODEL VS. INERTIA-ENHANCED MODEL

2.2 Dimensionality Reduction Algorithm for Multi-Feature Data

The modified ElasticNet method is employed to analyze the impact of different parameters on the mixer outlet temperature [17]. Features with high correlations with the outlet temperature are retained, whereas those with less influence are discarded, thereby reducing the dimensionality of the data and laying the foundation for the subsequent error prediction model.

Regression analysis is a common method for studying the interdependence of multiple variables. The linear regression model can be expressed as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \omega^i x^i = \theta^T X \quad (8)$$

where $\omega^i (i = 1, 2, \dots, p)$ represents the parameters to be estimated, $x^i (i = 1, 2, \dots, p)$ represents the feature variables in the dataset, n represents the sample size, p represents the number of feature variables, and $f(x)$ represents the output label, which in this case is the mixer outlet temperature. The main challenge in regression models lies in solving for the parameters $\omega^i (i = 1, 2, \dots, p)$ with the feature matrix and target output vector given by:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x^{00} & x^{01} & \dots & x^{0p} \\ x^{10} & x^{11} & \dots & x^{1p} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x^{n0} & x^{n1} & \dots & x^{np} \end{bmatrix}, Y \quad (9)$$

The estimation approach minimizes the error between the predicted and actual values, thus solving for the parameters, i.e., the objective function as follows:

$$\min_{\omega} \|\theta^T X - Y\|^2 \quad (10)$$

The key to the solution is to compute the generalized inverse matrix of the feature matrix $X^T X$. However, when the feature variables in a dataset exhibit strong correlations, the feature matrix may become ill-conditioned, making it difficult to estimate the parameters effectively. Additionally, when there are too many feature variables, overfitting may occur during the optimization process. To optimize the function and prevent overfitting, regularized regression is applied. This process involves adding a constraint term to the objective function.

Ridge regression employs an L_2 penalty, while LASSO regression applies an L_1 penalty [18]. LASSO may discard correlated but useful features, reducing model accuracy. To overcome this limitation, the ElasticNet algorithm [19] combines both penalties using a mixing parameter α [20, 21]:

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \min_{\theta} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{X}\theta\|^2 + \lambda \alpha \|\theta\|_1 + \frac{\lambda(1-\alpha)}{2} \|\theta\|_2^2 \quad (11)$$

Here, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the balance between LASSO ($\alpha = 1$) and ridge ($\alpha = 0$), while λ determines the overall strength of regularization.

The hyperparameters α and λ cannot be determined directly by the model and are typically selected through K-fold cross-validation. In K-fold cross-validation, the original dataset is divided into K subsets. Each subset is used once as the validation set, with the remaining K-1 subsets serving as the training set. The sum of the mean squared errors (MSEs) of the K models is averaged, and the value of λ corresponding to the minimum MSE is chosen as the optimal value. The expression for solving λ is as follows:

$$\lambda_{optical} = \arg \min_{\lambda} MSE_{avg}(\lambda) \quad (12)$$

$MSE_{avg}(\lambda)$ is as follows:

$$MSE_{avg}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K MSE(i) \quad (13)$$

In this study, a 5-fold cross-validation approach is employed to determine the optimal values of α and λ . The range of α is set to $[0, 1]$, with a step size of 0.05. The corresponding values of λ and the MSE for each α are calculated through 5-fold cross-validation. The parameter α and λ yielding the smallest MSEs are selected as the best-performing parameters.

Among the value of α within the range $[0, 1]$, the value of α that minimizes the error is 0.85, with a corresponding λ value of 0.00657. The relationship curve of the MSE with respect to λ at the optimal α value is shown in figure 4. Once the parameters are determined, feature selection is applied to the 11 variables in the dataset. The compression coefficients of each variable of the ElasticNet model are presented in table 2.

FIGURE 4: ERROR WITH RESPECT TO λ

Table 2: COMPRESSION COEFFICIENT OF EACH VARIABLE OF THE ELASTICNET MODEL

Variable	Compression coefficient	Variable	Compression coefficient	Variable	Compression coefficient
W_n	0.31	T_n	-0.08	P_{sec}	0
W_c	-0.09	P_c	-0.0149	T_{sec}	0
W_{sec}	0	T_c	0.0796	P_n	0.0288
P_{mix}	0				

2.3 Stacking Framework and Error Compensation Temperature Prediction Model

1. Mechanistic Model Based on Error Compensation

The fluid mixing process is influenced by multiple factors that are often neglected in mechanistic modeling. Variations in specific heat capacity before and after mixing, as well as heat transfer and wall friction, are typically ignored, leading to discrepancies between simulated and measured results. To address this, gradient boosting decision tree (GBDT) [22] is employed to reduce model errors. GBDT iteratively constructs subtrees based on the residuals between the mechanistic model outputs and actual values, progressively improving prediction accuracy.

2. Data-Driven Model

Machine learning algorithms generally require large datasets. In the prediction of the mixer outlet temperature, key variables include ambient air temperature and flow rate, as well as low-temperature air temperature, and flow rate. Support vector machine (SVM) algorithm [23] is well suited for nonlinear, high-dimensional regression tasks, enabling the integration of variables with both direct (temperature, flow rate) and indirect (pressure) effects on the outlet temperature.

Similarly, backpropagation (BP) algorithm [24] effectively capture complex nonlinear relationships. By learning the mapping between inputs (temperature, flow rate, pressure) and

output, BP neural network captures both the individual effects and the interactions among variables, thus enhancing its predictive performance for the mixer outlet temperature.

3. Prediction Model under the Stacking Framework

Stacking is an ensemble learning approach that integrates multiple base learners to improve prediction performance [25]. It offers strong interpretability, high accuracy, and suitability for complex datasets. The stacking framework comprises two layers: the first layer (Level 0) contains multiple base learners, whereas the second layer (Level 1) consists of a single meta-learner. A schematic diagram of the framework is shown in figure 5.

In the first layer of the stacking framework, BP and SVM algorithms, both effective for nonlinear prediction, are selected as base learners to enhance the learning capability. The random forest (RF) algorithm is adopted as the meta-learner in the second layer to improve generalization. In addition, a mechanistic error model is incorporated as a compensatory input at level 1. By combining mechanistic knowledge with data-driven learning, this model extracts latent features from time-series data and strengthens the framework's ability to capture the underlying dynamics, thereby improving overall predictive accuracy.

FIGURE 5: STACKING FRAMEWORK

The training procedure of the stacking-based temperature prediction method with error compensation is illustrated in figure 6 and can be summarized as follows:

1) Data partitioning: The dataset is divided into training and testing subsets. The testing set is constructed by combining a segment of multiple samples. The training set is used to train the temperature prediction model, whereas the testing set evaluates predictive performance.

2) Level 0 training: Base learners are trained using the training set. After training, the predicted outlet temperature vectors are concatenated to form a new feature matrix.

3) Error compensation modeling: The simulated outlet temperature from the mechanistic model and the actual temperature are used to train a gradient boosting decision tree (GBDT) error model, yielding error-compensated outputs.

4) Level 1 training: The new feature matrix from step 2 and the error compensation outputs from step 3 serve as input into the RF meta-learner, which is trained to produce final predictions on the testing set.

5) Performance evaluation: The evaluation metrics are calculated to assess the prediction results.

Figure 6: FLOWCHART OF THE PREDICTION METHOD BASED ON THE STACKING FRAMEWORK AND THE ERROR COMPENSATION MODEL

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the dataset used is obtained from high-altitude test data of a certain aero-engine, with a sampling interval of 0.2s. Model performance is evaluated using the root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute scaled error (MASE), and coefficient of determination (R^2). A lower RMSE and MASE, together with an R^2 value closer to 1, indicate higher predictive accuracy. The calculation formulas for these evaluation metrics are given as follows:

$$RMSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (14)$$

$$MASE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i)^2} \quad (16)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i represent the actual and predicted values at time i , respectively, and N is the number of samples.

3.1 Error Compensation Model Based on GBDT

Based on the mechanistic model established in Section 2.1, the simulated outlet temperature is first obtained. The simulated and actual values are then provided as inputs to the GBDT algorithm, with their errors as the output. In this manner, error compensation is applied to the mechanistic model predictions, yielding the final temperature estimates of the mixer.

As illustrated in figure 7, the prediction results show that although mechanistic model captures the general trend of the measured data, a considerable deviation remains. By incorporating the GBDT-based error compensation, this

deviation is substantially reduced, thereby confirming the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Figure 7: TEMPERATURE PREDICTION CURVE BASED ON GBDT ERROR COMPENSATION

3.2 Data-Driven Model

Data-driven models generally require substantial datasets for training. In this study, the features selected in section 2.2 are used as input features for each algorithm model, with the mixer outlet temperature as the prediction target. The predictive performance of individual data-driven models is first evaluated, and the results are presented in figure 8.

As shown in figure 8 and table 3, the SVM demonstrates relatively weaker performance. In particular, during the fourth data segment, its prediction trend deviates in the opposite direction from the actual measurements, although it still captures the overall variation trend and performs better than the GBDT model. In contrast, the RF model achieves a lower RMSE and an R^2 value closer to unity, indicating superior predictive accuracy compared with the other algorithms. Consequently, the RF algorithm is selected as the meta-learner for the second layer of the stacking framework.

(b) ENLARGED VIEW OF THE PREDICTION RESULTS FOR THE FOURTH SEGMENT

Figure 8: TEMPERATURE PREDICTION CURVE OF A SINGLE DATA-DRIVEN MODEL

Table 3: EVALUATION METRICS OF A SINGLE DATA-DRIVEN MODEL

Algorithm Model	Algorithm Parameter Set	Evaluation Metrics		
		RMSE	MAPE(%)	R ²
RF	Number of decision trees: 100 Minimum number of samples in a leaf: 5	2.1325	0.51	0.9622
SVM	Kernel function: Gaussian kernel Penalty coefficient C: 1	2.2311	0.66	0.9586
BP	Number of hidden layers: 10 Learning rate: 0.1	2.8812	0.74	0.9309
GBDT	Learning rate: 0.1	5.3095	1.48	0.7654

3.3 Performance Analysis of the Hybrid Prediction Model Based on the Stacking Framework

To demonstrate the advantages of the error-compensated model based on the mechanistic model, an ensemble learning strategy is first implemented within the stacking framework. In the first layer, BP and SVM models are used as base learners. This dataset is subsequently used as the input for the second-layer meta-learner, trained with the RF algorithm to generate the predicted mixer outlet temperature.

To further enhance predictive performance, the error model trained using the GBDT algorithm (Section 3.1) is incorporated as an additional input in the second layer. The hybrid model is compared with both the purely data-driven ensemble model and a single BP model using the validation set, thereby assessing the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed method.

Figure 9 illustrates the prediction curves of the three models. The RF algorithm, when used alone, performs poorest in the first

data segment. Although the data-driven ensemble model provides improved results, its predicted temperatures exhibit notable fluctuations, particularly in the fourth segment, where oscillations fail to capture the stable trend of the actual measurements.

The corresponding evaluation metrics are summarized in table 4. While the data-driven ensemble model and the hybrid model achieve similar RMSE values, the hybrid model attains a higher R², closer to 1, indicating superior overall predictive accuracy. Compared with the single BP model, the hybrid model reduces RMSE by 0.25% and improves R² by 1.97%, demonstrating its enhanced predictive capability.

Figure 9: PREDICTION CURVES OF THE OUTLET TEMPERATURE

Table 4: EVALUATION METRICS UNDER DIFFERENT MODEL COMBINATIONS

Algorithm Model	Evaluation Metrics		
	RMSE	MAPE(%)	R ²
RF	2.1325	0.51	0.9622
Data-Driven Combined Model	1.6882	0.26	0.9763
Stacking Framework Hybrid Model	1.5042	0.26	0.9812

4. CONCLUSION

A hybrid prediction method combining stacking and error compensation improves mixer outlet temperature prediction. Compared to single models, it reduces RMSE by 0.25% and increases R² by 1.97%. The method enhances generalization and reduces errors, showing clear practical value.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is supported by the Engine Thermophysical Test Apparatus, Grant No. E211010201.

REFERENCES

[1] Pei, X., Zhang, S., Dan, Z., Zhu, M., Qian, Q., and Wang, X., 2019, "Study on digital modeling and simulation of altitude test facility flight environment simulation system," *Journal of Propulsion Technology*, 40(05), pp. 1144-1152.

- [2] Zhu, M., Wang, X., Pei, X., Zhang, S., Dan, Z., Miao, K., Liu, J., and Jiang, Z., 2020, "Multi-volume fluid-solid heat transfer modeling for flight environment simulation system," *Journal of Propulsion Technology*, 41(12), pp. 2848-2859.
- [3] He, Z., 2023, "Study on Fuzzy Control Method of Large Range Airflow Temperature with Direct Mixture of Hot and Cold Gas," Master's thesis.
- [4] Huang, J., Ming, P., and Sun, W., 2023, "Dynamic modal analysis of fluid sweeping rods bundle," *Journal of Engineering Thermophysics*, 44(08), pp. 2279-2284.
- [5] Zhang, P., Li, Y., and Cheng, R., 2024, "Control of Corner Separation for a Linear Compressor Cascade via Bionic Slanting Riblets at the Endwall," *Journal of Thermal Science*, 34(1), pp. 1-16.
- [6] Zhu, D., 2022, "Structural optimization design of cold and hot airflow mixing chamber," Master's thesis, Huazhong University of Science and Technology.
- [7] Zhu, J., Dong, W., Wu, F., and Tian, X., 2011, "Calculation and analysis of heat transfer process in pipes of altitude test facility," *Gas Turbine Experiment and Research*, 24(04), pp. 10-14+24.
- [8] Montgomery, P., Burdette, R., Klepper, J., and Milhoan, A., 2002, "Evolution of a Turbine Engine Test Facility to Meet the Test Needs of Future Aircraft Systems," *American Society of Mechanical Engineers(ASME) Turbo Expo 2002 v.1: Aircraft Engine Coal, Biomass, and Alternative Fuels Combustion and Fuels Education Electric Power Vehicular and Small Turbomachines Amsterdam, The Netherlands*, pp. 119-128.
- [9] Montgomery, P. A., Burdette, R., Wilhite, L., and Salita, S., 2001, "Modernization of a Turbine Engine Test Facility Utilizing a Real-Time Facility Model and Simulation," *ASME TURBO EXPO 2001: Power for Land, Sea, & Air New Orleans, Louisiana, USA*, pp. 4474-4481.
- [10] Zhu, M., Wang, X., Pei, X., Zhang, S., Dan, Z., Liu, J., Miao, K., and Jiang, Z., 2020, "Temperature Delay Uncertainty μ Synthesis for Flight Environment Simulation System of Altitude Ground Test Facilities," *Journal OF Propulsion Technology*, 41(8), pp. 1861-1870.
- [11] Hajirahimi, Z., and Khashei, M., 2019, "Hybrid structures in time series modeling and forecasting: A review," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 86, pp. 83-106.
- [12] Wang, L., Wang, Z., Qu, H., and Liu, S., 2018, "Optimal Forecast Combination Based on Neural Networks for Time Series Forecasting," *Applied Soft Computing*, 66, pp. 1-17.
- [13] Ning, Z., Liu, X., and Wang, S., 2022, "A digital twin modeling approach for aerospace control systems with mechanism and data fusion," *Aerospace Control and Application*, 48(02), pp. 1-7.
- [14] Peng, L., 2020, "Soft measurement of temperature in vacuum sintering furnace based on mechanism and data-driven hybrid modeling," Master's thesis, Guangdong University of Technology.
- [15] Yu, G., 2021, "Research on neural network predictive control of decomposing furnace outlet temperature," Master's thesis, Hefei University of Technology.
- [16] Wang, J., Tang, W., Lv, T., and Ding, N., 2013, "Simulation theory and methods of pipeline networks," *Liaoning Chemical Industry*, 42(12), pp. 1476-1478.
- [17] Mi, D., Wang, T., Xiang, Y., and Du, W., 2020, "Elastic Net Based Online Assessment of Power System Transient Stability Margin," *Power System Technology* 44(1), pp. 19-26.
- [18] Tibshirani, R., 2011, "Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso: a retrospective," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)*, 73(3), pp. 267-288.
- [19] Zou, H., and Hastie, T., 2005, "Regularization and variable selection via the elastic net," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 67(5), pp. 768-768.
- [20] Barnwal, A., 2019, "Network Elastic Net for Identifying Smoking specific gene expression for lung cancer."
- [21] LI, J.-T., and JIA, Y.-M., 2010, "An Improved Elastic Net for Cancer Classification and Gene Selection," *Acta Automatica Sinica*, 36(7), pp. 976-981.
- [22] Friedman, J. H., 2001, "Greedy Function Approximation: A Gradient Boosting Machine," *The Annals of Statistics*, 29(5), pp. 1189-1232.
- [23] Cortes, C., and Vapnik, V., 1995, "Support-Vector Networks " *Machine Learning*, 20, pp. 273-297.
- [24] Lan, Z., Chen, J., Xue, C., Lan, J., Wang, B., Wang, Y., and Yang, Y., 2024, "A temperature control algorithm for lithography machine based on generalized predictive control and BP neural network PI control," *Measurement and Control*, 57(7), pp. 903-918.
- [25] Zhang, Y., Tian, Q., and Bai, Y., 2023, "Prediction of Outlet Temperature of Circulating Water Based on Hybrid Model and Stacking Framework," *Computer Simulation*, 40(05), pp. 172-177.